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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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The Influence of Social Skills of Social Studies Teachers on the Social Adjustment of Upper Basic Students in Delta State: A Correlational Study

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of social studies teachers' social skills on the social adjustment of upper basic students in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. Recognising the importance of teachers' emotional and social competencies in shaping student outcomes, this study draws on behaviourist and symbolic interactionist theories to understand the interplay between teacher behaviours and students' psychosocial development. A correlational survey design was adopted to explore the extent to which teachers' social skills influence students' ability to adjust within their academic and social environments. The population consisted of Basic Eight (JSS2) students and social studies teachers across eight public secondary schools selected from six local government areas using a stratified random sampling technique. A researcher-designed questionnaire validated by experts and tested for reliability was administered to participants. Data were analysed using Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression Analysis. Findings revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between social studies teachers' social skills and students' social adjustment. The regression model further demonstrated that teachers' social skills, when considered alongside gender and school location, had a significant combined effect on student adjustment, although only social skills made a strong individual contribution. The study concludes that social skills among teachers are critical determinants of students' emotional well-being, interpersonal relationships, and behavioural outcomes. It recommends targeted emotional intelligence training for teachers, integration of social-emotional learning modules into teacher education curricula, and greater investment in teacher support systems, particularly in rural

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schools. These findings have substantial implications for educational policy, teacher training, and classroom management in Nigeria's public secondary schools.

Keywords: Social skills, Social adjustment, Emotional intelligence, Social Studies teachers, Delta State

INTRODUCTION

Social adjustment is a critical aspect of adolescent development, particularly within the structured social environment of schools, where young individuals learn to navigate complex interpersonal relationships, manage emotions, and adhere to societal norms (Santrock, 2018). It encompasses the ability to form meaningful relationships, regulate behaviour, comply with institutional rules, and interact effectively with both peers and authority figures (Rubin, Bukowski, and Parker, 2006).

In recent years, educators and policymakers in Nigeria have expressed growing concern over a decline in students' social adjustment in public schools, reflected in increased truancy, aggressive behaviour, withdrawal from classroom activities, and frequent disciplinary infractions (Okafor, 2019; Nwankwo, 2021). Such behavioural patterns undermine not only the academic environment but also the overall well-being and future prospects of adolescents.

An often-overlooked factor in this problem is the social skills of teachers, who play a pivotal role in shaping the classroom's social climate (Wentzel, 2010). Teachers with strong interpersonal skills (such as empathy, effective communication, conflict resolution, and emotional regulation) are better able to build trusting relationships, manage classroom behaviour constructively, and create a supportive atmosphere that fosters positive social adjustment (Jennings and Greenberg, 2009). Social Studies teachers are uniquely positioned in this regard, as the subject inherently addresses social interaction, cooperation, values, and citizenship education (Banks, 2013).

However, research indicates that many teachers in Nigerian public schools lack formal training in emotional intelligence and social-emotional learning (SEL), limiting their ability to effectively guide students' psychosocial development (Okoro, 2020; Carmeli, 2003). This gap is particularly concerning in contexts where schools face structural challenges such as inadequate funding, high teacher-student ratios, and cultural barriers that compromise the quality of education (Federal Ministry of Education Nigeria, 2018).

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Teachers who model empathy, cooperation, and emotional regulation act as catalysts for positive behavioural change, promoting both social adjustment and academic engagement (Denham et al., 2012). Conversely, the absence of such competencies may reinforce maladaptive behaviours and widen the gap in student social adjustment (Pianta, Hamre, and Allen, 2012). Despite the significance of these factors, limited empirical evidence exists in the Nigerian context on how the social skills of social studies teachers specifically influence students' social adjustment outcomes.

This study addresses that gap by examining the extent to which social studies teachers' social skills affect the social adjustment of students in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. The findings are expected to inform teacher education, school administration, and policy reforms aimed at enhancing adolescent social development through improved teacher competencies and targeted interventions.

Objectives of the Study

This study was guided by the following objectives:

- i. To determine the relationship between social studies teachers' social skills and the social adjustment of upper basic students in Delta State.
- ii. To examine the joint influence of teachers' social skills, gender, and school location on students' social adjustment

Research Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following null hypotheses:

- i. There is no significant relationship between the social skills of social studies teachers and the social adjustment of upper basic students in Delta State.
- ii. There is no significant joint influence of social studies teachers' social skills, gender, and school location on the social adjustment of Upper Basic students in Delta State.

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Study Area

This study was conducted in public secondary schools located in Delta State, Nigeria. Specifically, it focused on Upper Basic students (Basic Eight or JSS2) and their social studies teachers across eight public secondary schools. These schools were selected from six different Local Government Areas (LGAs) within Delta State, using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure representation. Delta State, the southern region of Nigeria, features both urban and rural communities, which provided a diverse context for examining the influence of teachers' social skills on students' social adjustment in varying school environments.

THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In this study, two interrelated theories underpin the investigation: behaviourist theory and symbolic interactionism, each offering insight into how the social skills of social studies teachers can influence the social adjustment of upper basic students. These theories are complemented by a conceptual model adapted from Okorodudu (2016), which applies the Stimulus–Organism–Response (S–O–R) paradigm.

The behaviourist theory, particularly the work of Ivan Pavlov (1927) on classical conditioning and B.F. Skinner (1953) on operant conditioning, suggests that behaviour can be learnt, reinforced, or extinguished through interaction with environmental stimuli. In the context of this study, social studies teachers serve as external stimuli in the classroom. Their behaviours, ranging from verbal communication and feedback to tone, gestures, and interpersonal interactions, act as reinforcers or deterrents to student conduct. When teachers possess and exhibit strong social skills, they positively reinforce desirable behaviours such as cooperation, emotional control, and empathy among students. The theory further posits that consistent reinforcement of positive behaviour can lead to the internalisation of social norms. This is particularly relevant in adolescence, a developmental stage marked by susceptibility to external influences. Thus, when social studies teachers demonstrate attributes such as patience, approachability, and emotional stability, they condition students to mirror these behaviours, thereby promoting better social adjustment.

While the behaviourist approach focuses on conditioning and external stimuli, symbolic interactionism, as proposed by George Herbert Mead (1934) and later developed by Herbert Blumer (1969), offers a more interaction-based understanding of behaviour. This theory suggests that individuals derive meaning from social interactions

and internalise these meanings to guide their conduct. In the classroom, students interpret teachers' social signals – eye contact, tone of voice, praise, criticism, and gestures – as symbols that influence their self-concept, peer relations, and emotional behaviour. The implication of this theory is that social studies teachers, through their interpersonal conduct, shape not only the overt behaviour of students but also their internal understanding of what it means to be socially competent. Teachers who engage students respectfully and communicate expectations clearly help them form positive identities and navigate social situations more effectively. Conversely, teachers who exhibit poor communication, hostility, or inconsistency may inadvertently reinforce maladjustment, especially in students with limited external support systems.

The Stimulus–Organism–Response (S–O–R) Model

The conceptual framework for this study is drawn from Okorodudu's (2016) application of the Stimulus–Organism–Response (S–O–R) model to psychosocial development in educational settings. This model, which has its roots in behaviourist theory but incorporates interactionist insights, provides a structure for understanding how teachers' social skills (stimulus) interact with student-specific factors (organism) to produce behavioural outcomes (response).

Stimulus (S): In this context, the independent variable, social studies teachers' social skills, serves as the stimulus that influences student behaviour. This includes communication style, conflict resolution abilities, empathetic listening, and overall interpersonal conduct.

Organism (O): The organism represents the moderating variables of the student, such as gender, school location, and prior experiences, which mediate the way the stimulus is received and processed. For example, students in rural areas may respond differently to teacher behaviour due to differences in exposure, cultural values, or infrastructural resources.

Response (R): The response is the dependent variable, i.e., students' social adjustment. This includes the extent to which students are able to build friendships, resolve conflicts, participate in class, obey rules, and express themselves socially.

The S–O–R model is particularly suitable for studies involving behavioural outcomes, as it accounts not only for the direct influence of external factors but also the internal mechanisms through which such influences are filtered and responded to. Applied to the Nigerian context, especially in Delta State, this model helps explain

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how varying school environments, teacher attitudes, and student characteristics converge to produce specific adjustment patterns among students.

Together, these theories provide a robust framework for examining the role of teachers' social skills in shaping students' social behaviours. The behaviourist theory justifies the focus on external teacher conduct as a means of reinforcing behaviour, while symbolic interactionism explains how internal meanings and interpretations are formed through interaction. The S–O–R model combines both perspectives by demonstrating the pathway through which external teacher behaviour translates into observable student outcomes, moderated by internal and environmental variables. By integrating these perspectives, this study situates itself within a broader discourse on psychosocial development in education. It recognises that while academic instruction is central to the teacher's role, their social-emotional competence is equally vital in shaping the holistic development of students. In a culturally diverse and economically stratified context such as Delta State, understanding these dynamics is critical for designing interventions that promote inclusive, adaptive, and socially coherent learning environments.

Concept of Social Adjustment

Social adjustment refers to an individual's ability to align personal behaviour with social expectations, maintain positive interpersonal relationships, and respond appropriately to social cues (Romanczyk et al., 2005). In the school setting, it manifests through cooperation with peers, adherence to rules, active participation in group activities, and emotional stability. Goleman (2019) identifies social adjustment as a strong predictor of long-term academic achievement, peer acceptance, and psychological well-being.

Social skills, such as empathy, effective communication, active listening, and conflict resolution, are core components of emotional intelligence. Teachers who exhibit these skills tend to create supportive classroom climates, increase student engagement, and encourage positive behaviour. Carmeli (2003) found that individuals with strong social skills contribute to more harmonious work environments, while Schneider and Byrne (1995) emphasised their role in shaping student conduct. Adeyemo (2010) reported that both social skills and self-awareness significantly influenced students' adjustment during school transitions, and Mahesh (2015) observed a similar effect on social integration in upper basic classes.

Self-awareness allows teachers to recognise their own emotions, triggers, and biases, enabling them to make consistent and empathetic decisions. George (2000)

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linked teacher self-awareness to improved classroom management and student motivation. However, Shafa (2014) found no significant correlation between teacher self-awareness and student social adjustment, suggesting that contextual factors, such as school culture and student background, may mediate this relationship.

The influence of gender on social adjustment has produced mixed findings. Emore (2021) concluded that female students often display higher levels of adjustment due to better emotional regulation. In contrast, Ubogu (2022) found no significant link between gender and student social behaviour, arguing that teacher support and classroom climate are more decisive. Such inconsistencies highlight the importance of context-specific research. In Delta State, Nigeria, for example, prevailing gender norms and cultural expectations may shape adjustment patterns differently from other regions.

Location is another determinant of social adjustment. Urban schools often benefit from better facilities, smaller class sizes, and more socially competent teachers. Studies by Muheeb (2018) and Moronkola et al. (2004) reported that students in urban areas tend to adjust more effectively. Yet, Sumadeha (2016) cautioned that infrastructure alone is insufficient—teacher attitudes and interaction styles remain crucial.

A review of Nigerian literature reveals a scarcity of comprehensive studies examining social skills, self-awareness, gender, and location together as predictors of student adjustment. Prior works, including Adeyemo (2010), Bhatia (2012), and Opara and Onyekuru (2013), often isolated these variables or conducted research outside Delta State. This study addresses that gap by integrating these variables into a unified model, framed by behaviourist and symbolic interactionist perspectives, and focusing specifically on public secondary schools in Delta State to generate region-specific insights for educational improvement.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlational survey design to examine the relationship between social studies teachers' social skills and the social adjustment of Basic Eight students in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. The population included all social studies teachers and JSS2 students in the state, with a sample drawn from eight schools across six local government areas, representing urban and rural settings from the three senatorial districts. A stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure representation based on school location and gender distribution. Data were collected using a researcher-designed questionnaire, the Social Skills and Student Adjustment Questionnaire (SSSAQ), which included sections on demographic information,

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teachers' social skills, and students' social adjustment, measured on a 5-point Likert scale. The instrument was validated by experts in relevant fields and tested for reliability through a pilot study, yielding Cronbach's Alpha coefficients above the acceptable threshold. Formal permissions were secured from the Delta State Ministry of Education and participating schools before data collection, with questionnaires administered by the researcher and trained assistants while observing ethical standards such as informed consent and confidentiality. For data analysis, descriptive statistics described respondents' characteristics, while inferential statistics, including Pearson Product-Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression Analysis, were used to test hypotheses at the 0.05 significance level, utilising SPSS version 25. This methodology ensures rigorous, valid, and reliable findings applicable to the study's objectives.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

This section presents the statistical analyses and findings related to the research hypotheses. The analyses aim to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the social skills of Social Studies teachers and the social adjustment of Upper Basic students, and whether variables such as gender and school location make a meaningful contribution to this relationship.

Hypothesis 1 (H₀1):

There is no significant relationship between social skills of Social Studies teachers and social adjustment of students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.

To test this hypothesis, Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation was applied. The result revealed an R-value of 0.380, indicating a moderate positive relationship. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.145, meaning that approximately 14.5% of the variance in students' social adjustment is explained by the social skills of their teachers. The F-value obtained was 40.236, with a p-value of 0.000, which is below the significance threshold of 0.05.

Table 1: Pearson Correlation Analysis Between Teachers' Social Skills and Students' Social Adjustment

Statistic	Value
Pearson Correlation Coefficient (R)	0.380
Coefficient of Determination (R^2)	0.145
Significance Level (p-value)	0.000

Source: Researchers Field Data (2025)

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Table 2: ANOVA Summary for Regression Model

Source	F-value	p-value	Significance ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Regression	40.236	0.000	Significant

Source: Researchers Field Data (2025)

Interpretation: Since $p < 0.05$, the result is statistically significant.

Decision: The null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion: Social Studies teachers' social skills significantly influence students' social adjustment.

Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂):

There is no significant relationship among Social Studies teachers' social skills, gender, and location, and the social adjustment of students in Upper Basic Schools.

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to test this hypothesis. The R-value was 0.568, and R² was 0.323, indicating that 32.3% of the variance in students' social adjustment is jointly explained by teachers' social skills, gender, and location. The F-value was 22.347 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating statistical significance.

Table 3: Model Summary for Multiple Regression Analysis

Model Predictors	R	R ²	Interpretation
Teachers' Social Skills, Gender, and Location	0.568	0.323	32.3% of variance in students' social adjustment explained

Source: Researchers Field Data (2025)

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Table 4: ANOVA Summary for Multiple Regression Model

Source	F-value	p-value	Significance ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Regression	22.347	0.000	Significant

Source: Researchers Field Data (2025)

Table 5: Coefficients of Predictors on Students' Social Adjustment

Predictor	Unstandardized Coefficient (B)	Standardized Coefficient (β)	t-value	p-value	Significance ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Social Skills	0.399	0.336	6.203	0.000	Significant
Self-Awareness	0.502	0.412	7.611	0.000	Significant
Gender	-0.843	0.087	-1.349	0.179	Not Significant
Location	1.062	0.109	1.687	0.093	Not Significant

Source: Researchers Field Data (2025)

Interpretation: The regression model is statistically significant. However, only teachers' social skills and self-awareness made significant individual contributions. Gender and location were not individually significant.

Decision: Reject the null hypothesis.

Conclusion: There is a significant joint influence of the selected variables on students' social adjustment, with social skills and self-awareness being the key predictors.

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DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study provide compelling evidence that the social skills of social studies teachers significantly influence the social adjustment of upper basic students in public secondary schools in Delta State. The analysis confirmed a moderate positive correlation between these two variables, indicating that students taught by socially skilled teachers are more likely to demonstrate appropriate social behaviour, emotional regulation, and interpersonal competence. This outcome corroborates the findings of Carmeli (2003), who established that emotional and social competencies significantly enhance workplace dynamics and interpersonal relationships. Transposed into the educational setting, this means that teachers who possess effective communication skills, empathy, and conflict resolution abilities are more likely to establish classroom environments that support positive social behaviour. This aligns with Goleman's (2019) assertion that social skills are a core component of emotional intelligence, which directly affects one's ability to manage relationships and lead others effectively. Moreover, the result supports the work of Schneider and Byrne (1995), who argued that students respond positively to teachers who exhibit consistency, fairness, and understanding – key indicators of high social skill. Within the Nigerian educational context, Okorodudu (2016) similarly found that social studies teachers with higher levels of interpersonal competence were better able to manage behavioural challenges in the classroom and reduce instances of student maladjustment. The findings also align with Symbolic Interactionist Theory, which posits that individuals develop meaning through social interaction. Teachers serve as social models, and students often internalise the meanings conveyed through verbal and non-verbal interactions.

A teacher who engages students respectfully, listens actively, and uses encouraging language symbolically communicates positive values, which students learn to replicate in their interactions with peers. These findings affirm that the school setting, particularly teacher-student relationships, is a critical space where social identities are shaped. Interestingly, the study further revealed a statistically significant joint influence of teachers' social skills, gender, and school location on students' social adjustment, although only social skills showed a strong individual contribution. This finding adds a layer of nuance, suggesting that while demographic and contextual factors may play a role, it is ultimately the interpersonal competence of the teacher that exerts the most direct influence on student adjustment. This is consistent with the findings of Bhatia (2012), who reported that teacher behaviour has a stronger impact on

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student psychosocial development than demographic variables such as gender or geographical location. The apparent insignificance of gender and location as individual predictors in the regression analysis supports the argument advanced by Ubogu (2022) and Salovey and Mayer (2001) that student behaviour and adjustment are more heavily influenced by social context and relational factors than by inherent demographic characteristics. These scholars argue that even in structurally disadvantaged settings, students can thrive socially if they receive consistent emotional support from significant adults, particularly teachers. Furthermore, the combined R^2 value of 0.237, while moderate, is meaningful within educational research, where behavioural outcomes are influenced by multiple variables. The value suggests that nearly one-quarter of the variance in students' social adjustment can be explained by the combined effect of teachers' social skills, gender, and school location. This finding reinforces the relevance of the S–O–R (Stimulus–Organism–Response) model used in the conceptual framework of this study, which posits that external stimuli (teachers' social behaviour), filtered through individual characteristics (student gender, school type), result in observable behavioural outcomes (student adjustment).

The implications of these findings are profound. In a learning environment where academic performance is often prioritised over psychosocial development, these results call for a re-evaluation of teacher training and recruitment practices. The evidence suggests that investing in the emotional and interpersonal development of teachers can produce a more harmonious school climate and reduce incidences of indiscipline, alienation, and emotional distress among students. In summary, this study confirms that social studies teachers' social skills are not only desirable traits but also essential determinants of students' behavioural adjustment. The interaction between teacher behaviour and student response is dynamic, context-sensitive, and deeply rooted in psychological and sociological principles. By aligning with existing literature while also filling a critical gap in the Nigerian context, particularly in Delta State, this study adds value to the discourse on inclusive and emotionally responsive teaching.

CONCLUSION/ RECOMMENDATIONS

This study was conducted to examine the influence of Social Studies teachers' social skills on the social adjustment of Upper Basic students in public secondary schools across Delta State, Nigeria. Drawing on behaviourist and symbolic interactionist theories, the study investigated how teacher interpersonal competencies affect students' ability to navigate the social expectations of school life, form peer relationships, and

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exhibit socially appropriate behaviour. The findings reveal a statistically significant positive relationship between Social Studies teachers' social skills and students' social adjustment. The results further indicated that teachers' social skills, when considered alongside gender and school location, jointly influence student adjustment, although the teacher-related variable emerged as the only significant independent contributor. This suggests that regardless of gender and location, the presence of socially competent teachers is a strong predictor of students' ability to adapt socially within the school setting. These findings validate the assertion that effective teaching transcends the delivery of academic content. It involves nurturing the emotional and social dimensions of students' lives through positive interpersonal interaction, empathy, active listening, and conflict management. Teachers who possess and apply these social competencies not only foster an inclusive learning environment but also become role models through whom students internalise pro-social behaviours. In essence, the study affirms that the teacher-student relationship is foundational to psychosocial development during adolescence. The implications are particularly urgent in the Nigerian context, where issues of school discipline, social disconnection, and behavioural maladjustment continue to pose challenges to educational development. The success of any educational intervention aimed at improving student behaviour must therefore prioritise the emotional and social readiness of teachers.

Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that teacher training institutions include compulsory modules on emotional intelligence, communication, and social skills to better prepare teachers for managing diverse classrooms. State education ministries and school boards should provide ongoing professional development focused on interpersonal skills like empathy and conflict resolution, especially for Social Studies teachers. Schools should employ trained guidance counsellors to support students' social adjustment and collaborate with teachers in behaviour management. Priority should be given to recruiting and retaining socially skilled teachers in rural schools through incentives and support. Future research should use longitudinal designs to examine the long-term effects of teachers' social skills on student behaviour and academics, as well as the impact of school-wide social-emotional learning programs. Teacher recruitment and appraisal processes should assess interpersonal competence alongside subject expertise to promote effective teacher-student relationships. Implementing these recommendations will help integrate academic achievement with psychosocial development, fostering a more holistic approach to education in Nigerian public secondary schools.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

Dr. Samuel G. Etuk, Dr. Ini Smart Udoh, Oliver E. Idio

ISSN: 3026-9733

Green Marketing Activities And Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards Packaged Drinks In Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of green marketing indicators on consumer buying behaviour regarding packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The researcher considered indicators such as eco-friendly and recyclable packs, which were measured against consumer buying behaviour. The target population comprised all residents of Uyo, the state capital of Akwa Ibom State, who were assumed to have purchased some form of packaged drink, regarded as an infinite population. Slovin's formula was applied to determine a sample size of 400 respondents. The main source of data was primary, collected using a structured five-point Likert scale questionnaire. The data were analysed using simple linear regression at a 0.05 significance level. Findings showed that eco-friendly and recyclable packs have a positive and significant relationship with consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks. All null hypotheses were therefore rejected. It was recommended, among other things, that drink manufacturers should prioritise the use of recyclable packaging materials, especially plastics, as the quality of recycled plastic is a major factor influencing the market for drinks and causes little or no harm to the environment or the product itself.

Keywords:

INTRODUCTION

Green marketing has received considerable attention from marketing academics, practitioners, and consumers in Nigeria over the past few decades. The concept began to gain prominence in academic circles during the late 1980s and early 1990s. The inaugural workshop on *Ecological Marketing* was conducted by the American Marketing Association (AMA) in 1975, and its contents were subsequently published as *Ecological Marketing* in a seminar publication on the subject (Akter, 2012).

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

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ISSN: 3026-9733

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Globally, there has been a marked increase in consumer awareness and mindfulness regarding the consumption of goods and services. The depletion of natural resources and the resulting severe environmental damage have become major concerns (Chen and Chai, 2010). Significant consequences of environmental degradation include global warming, increased environmental pollution, and loss of biodiversity (Chen and Chai, 2010).

Similar to global trends, Nigerians are showing greater concern for environmental preservation. The core premise in understanding green marketing is that potential consumers perceive a product or service as “green” if it is environmentally friendly, safe, and socially responsible. Consequently, purchasing decisions may be influenced by this perception (Ebhote, 2019). To promote green marketing, regulatory agencies and legislation have been established in Nigeria to protect consumers from harmful products and ensure environmental safety (Rashad and Igbazua, 2011).

Substantial research has examined the effectiveness of green marketing on consumer purchasing. Some studies have tested the effect of eco-friendly products on brand image, while others have explored purchasing behaviours such as avoiding products deemed harmful or environmentally destructive. Rising health consciousness has also bolstered demand for packaged drinks, prompting manufacturers across major soft drink categories to diversify their portfolios.

In Nigeria, several green marketing studies have been conducted in different contexts and with various variables. Some have focused on organisational green strategies. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is limited empirical evidence on how green marketing proxies influence consumer buying behaviour for drinks specifically. This study therefore seeks to determine whether eco-friendly packs, recyclable packs, and product safety (safe for consumption)—as proxies of green marketing—are related to consumers' buying behaviour.

Objectives of the Study

While the main purpose of this study is to ascertain the level of association between green marketing indicators and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, the specific objectives were to:

- i. determine the influence that eco-friendly packs have on consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

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Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

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- ii. ascertain the effect that recyclable packs have on consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Hypotheses of the Study

The hypotheses formulated to guide the study were:

H₀1: Eco-friendly packs do not significantly influence consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

H₀2: There is no significant effect between recyclable packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Concept of Green Marketing

The notion of green marketing has been examined across multiple domains of marketing, including social marketing, ecological marketing, environmental marketing, and sustainable marketing (Soonthonsmai, 2001; Chamorro and Tomas, 2006). Yan and Yazdanifard (2014) note that researchers contend the concept was initially formulated in the late 1970s. Mishra and Sharma (2012) describe green marketing as an emerging strategy encompassing various initiatives, such as adopting fair-trade practices, modifying products, implementing sustainable production processes, and using eco-friendly packaging. The American Marketing Association (AMA) defines green marketing as the distribution and promotion of products that do not adversely affect the environment (Yazdanifard and Mercy, 2011).

From an environmental perspective, green marketing involves organisational initiatives to produce, promote, package, and recycle products in ways that demonstrate awareness of, and responsiveness to, ecological concerns. Saini (2013) defines “green” as a holistic concept encompassing products and practices characterised by their organic qualities, sustainability, and general environmental friendliness. The study asserts that green marketing entails promoting and selling products or services by highlighting their beneficial environmental characteristics. Saini (2013) further posits that a good or service is considered environmentally friendly if it offers intrinsic ecological advantages or is produced and/or packaged through sustainable methods. Consumers often associate terms such as *phosphate-free*, *recyclable*, *refillable*, and *ozone-safe* with green marketing (Zulfiqar and Shafaat, 2015). This study focuses on

green marketing indicators in packaged beverages that may influence consumer purchasing behaviour, particularly environmentally friendly and recyclable packaging.

Environmental (Eco)-Friendly Packaging

The significance of packaging is paramount across various product categories, as it attracts and inspires customers to select products. The use of materials and manufacturing techniques that minimise energy consumption and environmental impact is noteworthy (Jerda and Sahayaselvi, 2018). Packaging plays a significant role in influencing the choice of environmentally friendly products. As noted by Dantas et al. (2004), labels and packaging elements are crucial factors affecting consumer decisions. Grönman et al. (2012) assert that the primary function of packaging is to protect and deliver the appropriate product to the correct end-user in a secure, economically viable, and accessible manner. Consequently, packaging safeguards products against external factors and potential damage, ensuring their security throughout the supply chain (González-García et al., 2016). Williams and Wikström (2011) further highlight the role of packaging in reducing food waste and mitigating the environmental impact of the entire food packaging system.

Conceptually, the eco-friendliness of a product's packaging refers to the design, development, and delivery of packaging that prioritises environmental sustainability, thereby minimising harm to the environment and its stakeholders (Zia, 2012). The use of plastics, chemicals, and non-biodegradable materials is associated with numerous adverse effects, underscoring the advocacy for eco-friendly packaging (Patel et al., 2018).

Suherlan and Widiyanti (2021) identify five fundamental principles of packaging design. First, packaging acts as a wrapper that encapsulates the product's identity and intended use. Second, it serves as a protective barrier against impact, friction, and shock, making material durability essential. Third, packaging should be user-friendly, providing a pleasant tactile experience, being gentle to the touch, flexible in grip, easy to maintain, convenient to store, and stable when positioned, with priority given to recyclability. Fourth, packaging should effectively showcase the product image and indicate market segmentation, incorporating creativity, aesthetic appeal, and imaginative vision. Packaging reflects the user's social standing and the contexts in which the product is used, with distinctiveness being a foremost consideration. Fifth, packaging should embody environmental harmony. Jerda and Sahayaselvi (2018)

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

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ISSN: 3026-9733

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propose that the adoption of eco-friendly packaging by both manufacturers and consumers can reduce pollutants harmful to the atmosphere, soil, and oceans.

Prihandono et al. (2020) conducted a study in Indonesia examining the impact of green marketing tools, eco-friendly labels, and green advertising on consumer purchasing behaviour for mineral water. Using partial least squares analysis on data from 115 respondents, they found a positive and significant relationship between eco-friendly labelling and green advertising in influencing purchase decisions. They recommended that bottled water manufacturers implement green marketing campaigns targeting both regional and global markets to improve sales performance and address existing challenges.

Ishaswini and Datta (2011) conducted a study in India to assess consumers' environmental concerns, understanding of ecological issues, and awareness of sustainable products. The findings indicate that awareness of eco-friendly products and environmental concerns significantly influence green purchasing behaviour. The authors noted that packaging and labels capture consumer attention within seconds, yet it remains challenging for consumers to identify environmentally friendly products. Nevertheless, consumers demonstrate awareness of packaging attributes related to environmental considerations.

Recyclable Packs

Recycling entails the utilisation of reclaimed materials to produce a novel product (Hopewell et al., 2009). The incorporation of recycled materials in packaging presents significant advantages in terms of resource efficiency and reductions in carbon emissions. The extent of resources conserved and carbon emissions mitigated is contingent upon the proportion of recycled materials integrated within the packaging application and the recovery techniques utilised (British Plastics Federation – BPF, 2020). As articulated by Mostafa (2007), the acquisition of recyclable packaging products that pose no detriment to the environment constitutes a manifestation of environmentally conscious purchasing behaviour.

Materials utilised for packaging, including papers, paper boards, plastics, steel cans, and glass jars, serve the essential function of enclosing or safeguarding products throughout the processes of distribution, storage, sale, delivery, and utilisation. The selection and application of these packaging materials are contingent upon the nature of

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

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the products, associated costs, and the intended purpose of the packaging (Jang et al., 2020). Recyclable packaging utilised for beverages may manifest in the following forms:

- i. Paper and cardboard packaging:** Packaging made from paper and carton board demonstrates a high degree of recyclability. Nonetheless, the recycling of paper packaging is not an infinite process, as the fibres diminish in length and strength with each cycle of recycling (Kazulytė and Kruopienė, 2018).
- ii. Plastic packaging:** Plastics are utilised globally due to their safety in the packaging of food, beverages, pharmaceuticals, and products for children.
- iii. Glass packaging:** Glass packaging boasts an impressive recyclability rate approaching 100% and can undergo recycling processes indefinitely, maintaining its purity and quality with minimal degradation (Kazulytė and Kruopienė, 2018). Glass can be reused with confidence, as its chemical composition remains stable and does not leach into other substances. Consequently, glass recycling operates as a closed-loop system, generating neither supplementary waste nor products (Padmalatha and Shresta, 2016).
- iv. Metal packaging:** Metal packages possess the remarkable ability to be recycled indefinitely without any degradation in quality, ensuring that there is no occurrence of "down cycling" of materials; they seamlessly integrate into the material-to-material loop (Packaging Resources Action Group: PRAG, 2009).
- v. Composite packaging:** While the individual elements constituting composite packaging may possess the technical capacity for recycling, the practical challenges associated with sorting and separating materials, such as laminates and metallised films, effectively hinder the feasibility of recycling in real-world applications (Kazulytė and Kruopienė, 2018).

In 2019, Boateng conducted a study in Ghana aimed at identifying the factors related to packaging that affect consumer purchasing behaviour within the soft drink sector in Accra. The analysis of data gathered from 220 soft drink consumers in Accra indicates that plastic bottle packaging occupies the foremost position, followed by aluminium cans in second place, paper packaging in third, and glass bottle packaging in fourth,

reflecting the preferences within the soft drink industry in Accra, Ghana. The research reveals a noteworthy correlation between packaging and consumer purchasing behaviour. In light of the findings, it is advisable for soft drink manufacturers to focus on utilising plastic, aluminium cans, and paper as packaging options to effectively shape consumer purchasing behaviour, while simultaneously minimising the reliance on glass bottle packaging. Recycling serves as an evident strategy for waste management; however, it also exemplifies the application of industrial ecology in contemporary practice (Hopewell et al., 2009).

Consumer Buying Behaviour towards Packaged Drinks

Investigating consumer behaviour is crucial for comprehending the intricacies of product consumption and the various elements influencing the purchasing process of packaged goods (Santos et al., 2018). The dynamics of consumer buying behaviour extend beyond the mere act of purchasing products; it encompasses a comprehensive spectrum of activities, ranging from the initial recognition of a problem to the subsequent evaluation of experiences and ideas aimed at fulfilling their needs and desires (Mohamed et al. 2018). Consumer behaviour encompasses the examination of the processes engaged in the selection, acquisition, utilisation, or disposal of goods, services, ideas, or experiences by individuals, groups, and organisations, all aimed at fulfilling the needs and desires of consumers (Solomon et al. 2007). Kotler and Keller (2015) emphasise the significance of comprehending consumer buying behaviour, which is crucial for both manufacturers and service providers. The methods by which customers select products can greatly influence competitive advantage over rivals in numerous respects.

As environmental concerns increasingly resonate with the public, enterprises have started to adapt their production methods, the generation of goods or services, and, as a result, their marketing strategies. Organisations have commenced the production of sustainable and eco-conscious products.(Boztepe, 2012).Furthermore, enhancing the comprehension of consumer behaviour regarding environmentally friendly products is crucial, given the significant expansion of such products across all consumer sectors due to the prevailing 'green shift' and the strategic marketing approaches employed by numerous organisations.(Durif, Roy, and Boivin, 2012).

The green consumer is characterised as an individual who embraces environmentally conscious practices and opts for eco-friendly products in place of

conventional alternatives. Furthermore, environmentally conscious consumers exhibit a profound concern regarding the ecological ramifications stemming from their purchasing decisions. This category of consumers often believes that every individual, along with governments, businesses, and environmental advocates, has a significant role to play in consumerism and bears responsibility for environmental stewardship (Boztepe, 2012). Consequently, the assortment of products significantly influences the recognition of environmental sustainability and attributes of the product, potentially shaping consumer behaviour during the purchasing process.

As noted by Quazi (2008), the phenomenon of consumer buying behaviour, often termed 'consumerism', encompasses both micro and macro aspects of consumerist concerns. The micro-consumerist concerns encompass matters such as misbranding practices, misleading advertisements, deceptive packaging, and unfair pricing, among others. The overarching concerns of consumerism primarily engage with larger contexts such as environmental degradation, healthcare systems, nuclear opposition, and similar matters.

Conceptually, the framework for this study on green marketing indicators and consumer buying behaviour is presented as:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Green Marketing and Consumer Buying Behaviour

Source: *The Researcher's Construct (2023).*

Theoretical Framework

This study was fundamentally grounded in the theory of reasoned action. This social theory was formulated by Icek Ajzen and Martin Fishbein in 1975 and subsequently refined in 1980, as detailed in their publication "Understanding attitudes and predicting social behaviour: Attitudes, intentions, and perceived behavioural control." The theory aims to elucidate the

mechanisms through which attitudes exert influence over behaviour. The components that constitute the Theory of Reasoned Action include behavioural beliefs, assessments of behavioural outcomes that culminate in attitude, followed by normative beliefs and the motivation to comply, which together form subjective norms. The interplay between attitude and subjective norm culminates in the intention to engage in the behaviour, ultimately manifesting in the behaviour itself. This is represented in their model on Figure 2 below:

Figure 2: Theory of Reasoned Action – TRA (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975; 1980)

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Theory-of-Reasoned-Action-TRA-Fishbein-Ajzen-1975_fig1_284014676

It is essential to recognise that while the theory of reasoned action posits that behaviours are solely shaped by intentions, other scholarly works indicate that attitudes and prior actions have a direct impact on future behaviour (Bargh, 1997; Bentler and Speckart, 1979). This perspective suggests that an individual's present actions may be ingrained and elicited spontaneously by external cues.

This study elucidates how the theory of reasoned action provides insight into the mechanisms behind consumer product choices, particularly as they are influenced by environmental stimuli. Their awareness of the green attributes depicted on the product packaging influences their assessment of the product as environmentally friendly, potentially shaping their purchasing intentions and behavioural attitudes.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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METHODOLOGY

This study employed a survey research design approach. The research was conducted in Uyo, the capital of Akwa Ibom, with a population of 1,265,000 residents. The target respondents comprised individuals who consume or purchase packaged beverages of various types, representing a defined demographic within this population. The application of Slovin's Formula, set at a 5% margin of error, facilitated the determination of a suitable sample size for the study, maintaining a confidence level of 95%. The utilisation of the formula yielded a result of 399.8, which was rounded to approximately 400 and subsequently adopted as the sample size for the study. The study utilised a simple random sampling technique, and data were gathered through a survey questionnaire employing a five-point Likert scale.

The components of the research instrument underwent scrutiny by fellow scholars within the marketing discipline to assess both face validity and content validity. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability test was conducted as a preliminary assessment to evaluate the internal consistency of the items within the research instrument. The estimations of dependability that were acquired exceeded the 0.50 threshold, prompting us to advance with the analyses. The resulting coefficients of the items are summarised in Table 1 from Appendix I:

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha reliability Co-efficient of study variables

S/No.	Variables	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
1	Eco-friendly	3	0.922
2	Recyclable packs	3	0.667
3	Consumer buying behaviour	4	0.753
Total		10	0.781

Source: Data Analysis Output, 2023.

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Elektiv Publishing Group, USA

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DATA ANALYSIS

A total of 400 questionnaires were distributed to consumers of packaged drinks within the study area, of which 362 were retrieved and deemed usable, resulting in a response rate of 91 percent. The responses were subsequently analysed utilising the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 25.0). The descriptive characteristics of respondents are shown on Table 2:

Table 2: Descriptive Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
<u>Age</u>		
20-30 years	86	23.8
31-40 years	101	27.9
41-50 years	89	24.6
51 years and above	86	23.8
Total	362	100.0
<u>Gender of respondent</u>		
Male	193	54.1
Female	166	45.9
Total	362	100.0
<u>Educational Qualification</u>		
SSCE	72	19.9
Diploma/OND and Equivalent	98	27.1
HND/BSc/BA and Equivalent	103	28.5
Post Graduate and Equivalent	89	24.6
Total	362	100.0
<u>Attention to Environmental signs</u>		
Yes	191	52.8
No	171	47.2
	362	

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Total		
Frequency of Purchase		
Frequently	212	58.6
Occasionally (Depending on the product)	150	41.4
Total	362	100.0

Source: The Researcher's Compilation (2023).

Table 2 shows that shoppers/consumers aged 31–40 years (27.9%) constituted the largest proportion of respondents, followed by those aged 41–50 years (24.6%), 20–30 years (23.8%), and 51 years and above (23.8%). The results also indicate that 193 males (54.1%) participated in the study, compared with 166 females (45.9%). The table further reveals that 103 respondents (28.5%) possessed an HND, BSc, BA, or equivalent qualification, while 98 respondents (27.1%) held a Diploma, OND, or equivalent. In addition, 89 respondents (24.6%) had a postgraduate qualification or equivalent, and 72 respondents (19.9%) possessed a Senior Secondary Certificate (O'Level) as their highest educational attainment.

The implication of these results is that the study was gender-inclusive, and all participants were sufficiently educated to comprehend the subject under study and provide informed responses to the survey questions. When asked whether they paid close attention to environmental signs and messages on product packaging while shopping, 191 respondents (52.8%) indicated that they did, while 171 (47.2%) acknowledged being aware of such messages but not paying close attention to them while shopping.

Respondents were also asked how often they purchased packaged drinks of any kind (including bottled, canned, and paper-packed water, soft drinks, alcoholic drinks, juice, and similar beverages). The results showed that 212 respondents (58.6%) frequently purchased packaged drinks, while 150 respondents (41.4%) purchased them occasionally, depending on the product and the need. The implication of this finding is that all respondents were familiar with the research topic and could relate to the subject matter.

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Test of Hypotheses

H₀1: Eco-friendly packs do not significantly influence consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3 : Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.792 ^a	.628	.627	1.44601

a. Predictors: (Constant), Eco-Friendly

Table 4: ANOVA ^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1270.883	1	1270.883	607.8	.000 ^b
	Residual	752.744	360	2.091		
	Total	2023.627	361			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Eco-Friendly

Table 5: Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.540	.406		3.790	.000
	Eco-Friendly	.846	.034	.792	24.654	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer behaviour

Source: *The Researcher's Computation (2023).*

Results from the table show that the independent variable 'eco-friendly packs' ($X_1 = Ef$) explained approximately 63% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks with an $R^2 = 0.628$. This means that eco-friendly packs, considered as a green marketing indicator, were able to account for 63% of the changes in consumer buying behaviour. The result reveals that the relationship between eco-friendly packs (Ef) and consumer buying behaviour (Cb) was very strong according to $R = 0.708$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.627$, indicating that the regression model of this study is said to have a very strong explanatory power of the dependent variable.

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In addition, the F-ratio = 607.800 and p-value < 0.000 on the ANOVA suggest that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that eco-friendly packs significantly predicted the changes in the dependent variable (consumer buying behaviour). To evaluate the degree of change between the independent variable and the dependent variable, the value of the beta coefficients for eco-friendly packs (EF) had a statistically significant unstandardised coefficient of $\beta_{x1} = 0.846$ and p-value = 0.000, indicating a positive significant relationship with consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks. This finding can be interpreted to mean that every unit change in eco-friendly packs will result in a 0.846 increase in consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks, all other factors being held constant. The resulting simple linear model is represented as:

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + e$$

$$Y = 1.540 + 0.846 X_1$$

$$Cb = 1.540 + 0.846 Ef$$

However, since the significant p-value is less than 0.05 (Sig. p-value=0.000<0.05), it is concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between eco-friendly packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Akwa Ibom State. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

H₀2: There is no significant effect between recyclable packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.773 ^a	.598	.59	1.50291

a. Predictors: (Constant), Recyclable

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Table 5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1210.485	1	1210.485	535.915	.000 ^b
	Residual	813.142	360	2.259		
	Total	2023.627	361			61

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer buying behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Recyclable

Table 6 :Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.373	.440		3.123	.002
	Recyclable packs	.855	.037	.773	23.150	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer buying behaviour

Source: *The Researcher's Computation (2023).*

Results on the table show that the independent variable Recyclable Packs ($X_2 = R_p$) explained approximately 60% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks with an $R^2 = 0.598$. This means that recyclable packs, considered as a green marketing indicator, were able to account for 60% of the changes in consumer buying behaviour. The result reveals that the relationship between Recyclable Packs (R_p) and consumer buying behaviour (C_b) was strong according to the $R = 0.773$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.597$, indicating that the regression model of this study is said to have a strong explanatory power of the dependent variable.

In addition, the F-ratio = 535.915 and p-value < 0.000 on the ANOVA suggest that the results of the regression model could not have occurred by chance and that recyclable packs significantly predicted the changes in the dependent variable (consumer buying behaviour). To evaluate the degree of change between the independent variable and the

dependent variable, the value of the beta coefficients for Recyclable Packs (Rp) had a statistically significant unstandardised coefficient of $\beta_2 = 0.855$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.000$, indicating a positive significant relationship with consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks. This finding can be interpreted to mean that every unit change made in making the packs recyclable will result in a 0.855 increase in consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks, all other factors being held constant. The resulting simple linear model is represented as as:

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_2 X_2 \dots + e$$

$$Y = 1.373 + 0.855 X_2$$

$$Cb = 1.373 + 0.855 Rp$$

Since the significant $p\text{-value}$ is less than 0.05 (Sig. $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$), it is concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between recyclable packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion

Findings from the first hypothesis test revealed a significant positive relationship between eco-friendly packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Akwa Ibom State, with a regression coefficient of $R^2 = 0.628$ and a $p\text{-value}$ of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. This indicates that the independent variable, X_1 (eco-friendly packs = Ef), explained approximately 63% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks. This implies that ecological elements of product packaging, such as the materials used, environmentally friendly features, and decomposable nature, affect consumer buying behaviour in the state. This finding contrasts with Ebhote (2019), whose study revealed no significant relationship between eco-labelling, eco-friendly packs, and competitive advantage. Conversely, Prihandono et al. (2020) found that eco-friendly labels and packs were significantly related to consumer purchase decisions for bottled water, recommending that bottled water manufacturers implement green marketing campaigns suited to both regional and global markets to improve sales performance.

Findings from the second hypothesis test showed a significant positive relationship between recyclable packs and consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks in Akwa Ibom State, with a regression coefficient of $R^2 = 0.598$ and a $p\text{-value}$ of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. This indicates that the independent variable, X_4 (recyclable packs = Rp), accounted for 60% of the variation in consumer buying behaviour. This suggests that the use of recyclable or reusable organic packaging, particularly paper, glass, plastic,

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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and cardboard, and to a lesser extent wood and aluminium, was perceived as a socially responsible initiative by drink companies, influencing consumer purchasing decisions. This finding aligns with Boateng (2019), who noted that the use of plastic, aluminium cans, and paper as packaging, which can either decompose or be recycled, could influence consumer buying behaviour while reducing reliance on glass bottle packaging.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

The study's findings demonstrate that green marketing significantly influences consumer buying behaviour for packaged drinks. This implies that drink manufacturers employing green marketing strategies can shape consumer purchasing decisions by emphasising eco-friendly and recyclable packaging as healthy, environmentally responsible practices, thereby appealing to environmentally conscious consumers. It is concluded that eco-friendly packs and recyclable packs are significant predictors of consumer buying behaviour for packaged drinks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

On the basis of the study's findings, it is recommended that:

- i. The significant positive influence of eco-friendly packs on consumer buying behaviour of packaged drinks suggests that manufacturers should use biodegradable materials in packaging their products.
- ii. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that manufacturers of drinks should prioritise the use of recyclable materials for packaging, especially those made of plastics. This is because the quality of recycled plastic is another main factor that influences the market for products like drinks, and it causes little or no harm to the environment directly as well as the product itself.

Suggestions for Further Studies

This study has a number of observed limitations that should be addressed in further research studies. The domain of this research study was limited to consumers of packaged drinks in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. However, further studies may adopt the variables used in this study to ascertain consumers' preferences for fast-moving consumer goods based on their package type. Such studies may even be undertaken to

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Elektiv Publishing Group, USA

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ISSN: 3026-9733

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assess the quality implication of package materials used for consumables and also assess word-of-mouth information as a strategy for creating consumer awareness on green marketing.

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Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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Principals' Disciplinary Techniques and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to examine the extent of the relationship between principals' discipline techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. To achieve this purpose, seven objectives, seven research questions and seven null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all 762 principals and 7,607 teachers drawn from the 254 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The sample of this study consisted of 381 principals representing 50% of the population and 1,481 teachers representing 30% of the teaching population, giving a total of 1,862 respondents. A multistage sampling technique was adopted for the study, whereby purposive and stratified sampling techniques were used for the selection. Two researchers developed instruments tagged the Principals' Discipline Techniques Questionnaire (PDTQ) and the Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ), which were used for data collection. The validity of the instruments was established using the face validation method. The reliability of the instruments was established using the Cronbach alpha analysis method, which yielded reliability coefficients of .81 and .90 for the independent and the dependent variables, respectively. Regression coefficient was used to answer the research questions, while simple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The results of the analyses revealed that discipline technique has a significant relationship with teachers' job performance. Based on the findings, it was recommended, among others, that principals should adopt stringent disciplinary measures in order to improve teachers' job performance.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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INTRODUCTION

Education is a vital tool for the development of any society. It ensures the acquisition of the necessary skills, orientation, knowledge and values required in everyday activities which are essential in the development of the society. In essence, the level of development of any society is a true reflection of its educational development.

In Nigeria, the belief of the citizens is that the higher the level of educational attainment, the better the conditions of living and the overall development of the citizens. Hence, education has been adopted as an instrument for effecting national development (FRN, 2013). The experienced societal vices, insurgencies, moral decadence, drug abuse, human trafficking, and political and religious crises are seen as effects of the low-level and poor-quality education. The quality of education that is obtainable in some of our public secondary schools is such that it barely equips the school leavers with the necessary skills to emancipate themselves from poverty and joblessness and foster societal development.

It has been observed that with the introduction of free and compulsory education, the public secondary schools are experiencing a tremendous increase in enrolment rate without a corresponding increase in teachers' employment and infrastructures, including the building of new schools to cater for the teeming student population. This has posed a serious challenge to the management of schools as well as teachers' job performance. Due to inadequate classroom accommodation, some schools at times resort to converting staff rooms to classrooms, making teachers unable to settle after lessons. This has made it sometimes impossible for proper supervision of teachers by the principals; some of them only come to schools when they have lessons and leave the school anytime they are tired of roaming. Unconducive learning environment with inadequate infrastructure may also pose a problem to the effective job performance of the teachers as well as a managerial challenge in terms of effective administration. In some schools, teachers could not evidently give their principals feedback with meaningful contributions that may help the growth of the school system; some principals seldom communicate with their teachers on the way forward as a result of poor working conditions and at times due to unnecessary bureaucratic principles which may not allow a free flow of information, thus reducing teachers' morale and thus affecting their performance.

The success or failure of any school system depends to a large extent on the managers (principals), teachers, their quality, their commitment to duty and their

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ISSN: 3026-9733

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effectiveness on the job. The task of bringing about desired learning outcomes in the learners to achieve a nation's goal of education rests on principals' and teachers' competences. The overall school's performance depends largely on management effectiveness and teachers' commitment to work.

The management techniques of the principal as a chief administrator of the secondary school could play a significant role in determining the level of teachers' performance and commitment to teaching, which in turn could enhance learning processes and outcomes. Management techniques are systematic and analytical methods used to assist in decision-making, the improvement of efficiency and effectiveness and, in particular, the conduct of the two key managerial activities of planning and control (Heine 2010). Management techniques as tools that managers use to keep positive team morale, improve productivity and develop new talents. It involves helping to boost employees' morale to work towards organisational goal attainment. It consists of specified and often sequential methods of tackling a problem, providing information for decision-making or improving operational efficiency. Iwhiwhu (2010) maintained that management techniques deal with every aspect of a situation that describes possible measures for goal achievement.

Obviously, principals' management techniques may not be effective without a corresponding effort by teachers' performance, which entails the discharge of obligatory functions that are task-orientated and aimed at achieving defined goals (Asiyai, 2005). Teachers' performance is encompassing, as it involves the discharge of some defined tasks necessary to bring about desirable teaching and learning outcomes. Such tasks include classroom management aimed at effective and efficient utilisation of available human and material resources for the attainment of organisational goals. The classroom teacher is charged with lots of functions to perform in the teaching and learning processes. One of the most challenging tasks is classroom management and control. The teachers' effectiveness in teaching is assessed by the ability to use varied classroom management techniques to direct students towards effective and meaningful learning during instruction. Meaningful teaching and learning cannot be achieved in a classroom environment characterised by rowdiness, crowdedness, noise-making and distractions (Oyira, 2004). Educational objectives cannot be fully achieved without the use of a conducive classroom environment since the classroom is the meeting point for both teachers and students where curricular activities are implemented.

Close observation of our public secondary schools across the state does not depict conducive classroom situations. Teachers are made to teach in a class of 80-100

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ISSN: 3026-9733

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students at a time, in violation of the mandatory teacher-student ratio of 1:40 recommended by the National Policy on Education (FRN 2013). These crowded classes could sometimes lead to ineffectiveness of teachers in their job performance. Other teachers' tasks include lesson preparation and presentation, students' continuous assessment and evaluation, administration of examinations, improvisation/use of instructional materials, completion of scheme of work, introduction of innovations for lesson comprehension and retention, and presentation of results, among others. A good number of the teachers' tasks are executed in the classroom with the use of necessary infrastructure, which must be inevitably available before teaching and learning processes can flow. However, it is evident that the number of teachers in our secondary schools is grossly inadequate, facilities are either unavailable or not enough, accommodation is insufficient to cater for the teeming student population, some structures are dilapidated with no replacement, new schools are not being built to ease the overcrowding problem, and a lot more could likely reduce teachers' morale, affect general cooperation with school authority, discourage meaningful contributions and in turn could lead to poor job performance.

Deductively, measurement of teachers' performance seems to be based on two criteria, namely, the effectiveness paradigm, which uses students' outcome (usually achievement), and the teaching process paradigm, which focuses on various aspects of teachers' and students' behaviour judged to be worthwhile in their own right or linked to students' achievement (Iyede, 2001). Evaluating teachers' performance using the performance criterion has attracted much attention. In Nigeria, the general belief is that performing teachers must produce performing students. Poor academic performance of students in Nigeria has therefore been linked to poor teachers' performance in terms of accomplishing the teaching task, negative attitude to work and poor teaching habits, which have been attributed to poor management (Ofoegbu, 2004).

As a leader in the school system, the principal's administrative competence in the areas of supervision, communication, mentoring, decision-making, capacity building, disciplinary measures, conflict management, and others could be adopted as management techniques which may be important in directing the thrust, dynamics and trends of teaching and learning in secondary schools. Thus, the overall school administration is tested by these variables.

Disciplinary measures are those steps taken by a school administrator to ensure compliance with school rules and regulations. The principal, as the manager of the school, is vested with the responsibility of instilling discipline among teachers. The

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Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

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ISSN: 3026-9733

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term 'discipline' in an organisation implies meaningful co-ordination and control of personnel which prompts that organisation to conform to the prescribed code of conduct framed for their guidance (Reddy, 2004). Discipline aims at establishing a human relations climate based on mutual trust, confidence and respect in superior-subordinate working relationships. Jucious (2008) maintained that discipline is said to be good when employees willingly follow the rules of their superiors.

Where principals neglect the aspect of discipline in schools, teachers show a high rate of absenteeism, lateness to work, dereliction of duty, insubordination, disrespect to constituted authority, laxity and a high rate of attrition, which inhibits proper teaching and completion of the scheme of work and projects a bad example for students who may look on teachers as role models. With proper disciplinary measures, teachers stand the ground of discharging their duties effectively.

Research Hypothesis

To guide the study, the following null hypothesis was formulated:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between principals' disciplinary techniques and teachers' job performance in Akwa Ibom State.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study

The correlational research design was adopted for this study. This design was considered appropriate as it sought to measure the existing relationship between the independent variable (principals' management techniques) and the dependent variable (teachers' job performance). In this type of design, it is both impracticable and unethical for the researcher to manipulate any of the variables; rather, the emphasis is on describing the natural course of events as they occur (McCombes, 2009). The study, therefore, aimed to determine the extent of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised all principals, vice principals (academic), and vice principals (administration/special duties), totalling 762, as well as all 7,607 teachers in the 254 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State during the

2019/2020 academic session (SEB, 2019).

Sample and Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was employed for this study. Purposive, stratified, and cluster sampling methods were used to include vice principals of academics, administration, and special duties, owing to their administrative responsibilities, alongside principals. Public secondary schools were stratified across the three senatorial districts of the state. Within each district, schools were clustered into local government areas, taking into account the number of schools, principals, and teachers in each zone. This yielded:

- **Senatorial Districts:** 9, 12, and 10 Local Government Areas, respectively
- **Public Secondary Schools:** 89, 72, and 93
- **Principals:** 89, 72, and 93
- **Teachers:** 3,453, 1,294, and 2,860, respectively

From this distribution, simple random sampling was applied to select 160 public secondary schools (representing 50% of the population across the senatorial districts), 381 principals (50%), and 1,481 teachers (30%). This produced a total sample size of 1,862 respondents.

To ensure adequate representation, at least 12 teachers were sampled in each school. Each principal rated a minimum of four teachers, while four teachers rated each principal. This established a principal–teacher ratio of 1:4 and a teacher–principal ratio of 4:1. (See Appendix I for the sampling frame).

Instrumentation

Two research instruments were developed by the researcher to generate data:

i. Principals' Discipline Techniques Questionnaire (PDTQ)

- Designed to measure principals' management techniques, focusing on seven sub-variables.
- Each category comprised eight items, yielding a total of 56 items.
- The PDTQ was rated by teachers.

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Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

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ISSN: 3026-9733

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ii. Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)

- Developed to measure indicators of teachers' performance such as classroom management, lesson delivery, student evaluation, introduction of innovations, and mastery of lesson content.
- The TJPQ contained 20 items.
- The TJPQ was rated by principals.

Method of Data Analysis

The regression coefficient was employed to answer the research questions, while simple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between principals' disciplinary techniques and teachers' job performance in Akwa Ibom State.

Simple regression analysis was used to test the null hypothesis and summary data shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Simple regression analysis of relationship between principals' disciplinary technique and teachers' job performance

Variables	Source of Variable	SS	Df	MS	F-value	P-value	Decision p<.05
Principals'	Regression	236637.903	1	236637.903	disciplinary	Technique	
Teachers' job performance	Residual	434801.012	1421	305982	773.37	.000	Significant

Significant P<.05

Source: Researcher field work (2021).

Total 671438.915 1422

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ISSN: 3026-9733

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The result in Table 4.1 reveals that the calculated F-value was 773.371 and the calculated P-value was .000, which was less than the F-value at the .05 level of significance with 1422 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis, which stated that the extent of the relationship between principals' disciplinary technique and teachers' job performance is not significant, was rejected. Hence, the extent of the relationship between principals' disciplinary technique and teachers' job performance is significant.

Discussion of Findings

The main focus of this study was to determine the extent of the relationship between principals' disciplinary techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. From the findings of the research, it has been revealed that the extent of the relationship between principals' management techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State is significant. The following discussions presented below are based on the results of the hypotheses raised in the study.

Disciplinary Technique and Teachers' Job Performance

The extent of the relationship between principals' disciplinary technique and teachers' job performance is significant. The direction of this finding gives credence to the fact that discipline is important in ensuring that school objectives are achieved and that teachers behave well in consonance with school rules and regulations as well as teachers' professional ethics. This result is eminent considering the role of discipline in educational institutions; it affects the achievement of educational objectives. The finding agrees with the views of Chisholm (2007), "that disciplined teachers produce disciplined learners and positively impact on the overall school goals attainment".

In a study by Nguni (2005) on the relationship between teachers' perception of the behaviour of the school organisation and the teachers' perception of discipline relating to organisational effectiveness, a random sampling of 250 teachers each from 10 secondary schools randomly selected from the metropolitan Nashville public school system received questionnaires. 159 of those randomly selected teachers participated in the study and returned their completed questionnaire. The specimen rank co-efficient of correlation product was used for organising and summarising the data and thereby determining the level of discipline. Based on the findings, it was concluded that a

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relationship existed between managerial techniques and perception of discipline effectiveness. Also, there was a relationship between the psychological state of people who work in school organisations and their perception of discipline effectiveness. Teachers working in school organisations which are intellectually supportive or structured and work-orientated seem to perceive the prevailing discipline in the school as effective. It is likely that an unhealthy school environment is related to the high incidence of poor teacher job performance.

This implies that teachers are meant to be role models to their learners and that the level of comportment and decency in behaviour exhibited by teachers has a direct influence on students and the school's success at large.

This finding is in tandem with the position of Cabanes (2017:44), “that a principal that uses supportive discipline, corrective discipline, verbal and written warnings where necessary and appropriate sanctions on erring teachers within prescribed policy is bound to create a humorous and enabling atmosphere for effective learning, and achievement of desirable outcomes becomes obvious.” This entails that a disciplined teacher is bound to produce a quality service for improved job performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that principals' disciplinary techniques have a significant relationship with teachers' job performance. Discipline serves as an essential mechanism for guiding teachers' professional conduct, ensuring compliance with institutional rules and regulations, and promoting the attainment of educational objectives. Consequently, effective application of disciplinary measures by school principals enhances teachers' job performance and contributes to the overall success of the school system.

Since principals' disciplinary techniques exert a significant influence on teachers' job performance, school leaders should ensure that appropriate sanctions are consistently imposed on erring teachers within the framework of established policies. Such sanctions should serve both as corrective measures and deterrents to others, thereby fostering professionalism, accountability, and improved teacher performance.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 3, AUGUST, 2025

ISSN: 3026-9733

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